

The influence of Electronic Health Record systems on the quality of healthcare services: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract. Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems have significantly impacted healthcare services, bringing about both great opportunities and challenges. To improve healthcare services quality, the World Health Organisation (WHO) has recommended their adoption globally and particularly, implementation of open-source software. This paper thus examined the influence of EHR systems on the quality of healthcare services delivery. Qualitative approaches were employed to conduct a systematic literature review (SLR) design. The SLR design also incorporated the Gioia Methodology for data analysis, synthesising 29 articles from Cochrane, CINAHL, and PubMed. Six key themes considering the EHR system influence on quality healthcare services delivery were revealed: safety, effectiveness, patient-centeredness, timeliness, equitability, and efficiency. The benefits and challenges of using EHR systems to enhance the quality of healthcare services delivery were shown to be spread across the six themes.

Keywords: Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems, services delivery, quality healthcare.

1 INTRODUCTION

Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems have gained popularity in use at various healthcare facilities globally [1], [2]. The systems particularly developed on open-source software have gained relatively wide adoption, especially in resource-constrained environments [3], [4]. The World Health Organisation (WHO) posits that, to achieve the goal of universal health coverage, implementation of EHR systems in healthcare facilities must be prioritised [1], [2]. They also suggested that, in the interest of resource-constrained countries, it is advisable that health facilities implement open-source software solutions as opposed to proprietary software [5], [6]. The financial implications associated with these developments were found to be favourable for such health facilities like those in resource-constrained environments.

Some research state that there are numerous benefits that can be realised using open source EHR systems [2], [3], [4], [5], [6]. Several opportunities have been reported by facilities that adopted EHR systems. These include inter alia, better reporting and decision-making, improvements in data quality and availability, improved quality of service delivery, and the function of interoperability [6]. While other well established

health facilities opt for proprietary EHR systems, the cost benefit analyses indicate they are more costly than using open-source ones [6]. However, despite the popularity of open-source EHR systems in healthcare facilities in other settings, there is still room for studies that consolidate and report on their uses to either constrain or enable quality healthcare services delivery in healthcare facilities using a systematic literature review approach. This gap hinders knowledge contribution endeavours on how EHR systems may be used to realise their full benefits as reported by researchers in different settings of healthcare services provision, a contribution this study makes.

As such, the aim of this review, through a systematic literature review (SLR) protocol, and without squarely focussing only on open-source software, is to examine the influence of EHR systems on quality healthcare services delivery for healthcare facilities. The study was thus guided by the following research question: ***“How do EHR systems influence quality healthcare services delivery in healthcare facilities?”*** This question led to the study’s objective, which is: ***“To examine the influence of EHR systems on quality healthcare services delivery in healthcare facilities.”***

This research contributes to scholarly literature by offering an understanding on the use of EHR applications to enhance the quality of services provision within healthcare processes. Practically, understanding better use of these EHR applications assists the custodians of the systems in improving services delivery, thereby enabling stakeholders to map strategies to mitigate common service constraints while also improving ways to fully benefit from the EHR systems. This contribution would not be fully understood without the working definition of what the study means by quality healthcare services delivery. As such, the concept of quality healthcare services delivery, based on the findings of this inquiry, is the process of providing health services that consistently increase the likelihood of desired health outcomes, while meeting the standards of *safety, effectiveness, patient-centredness, timeliness, equitability, and efficiency* [7], [8], [9] (the six themes formulated in the analysis section). Subsequently, methodologically, this SLR approach combines thematic analysis with the Gioia Protocol or Methodology (a derivative of the Grounded Theory methodologies and techniques) in the analysis of the articles [10], [11], [12]. This contributes to literature review methodological approaches, adding rigour to one of the most utilised traditional analyses methods applied on qualitative SLR approaches.

The rest of the paper is categorised into four more sections. The following section details the design and methodological processes employed to conduct a rigorous stand-alone literature review. It details the review protocol, for which a SLR approach coupled with the PRISMA framework were utilised. The third section details using the Gioia Methodology (GM) techniques, how data were coded and analysed. This is followed by the discussion section, where themes from the analyses are explicated. Finally, the paper presents concluding remarks which also incorporate limitations and suggestions for future work.

2 METHODS

Stand-alone literature reviews have in the recent years gained popularity within various academic fields [13]. This practice has been driven by the growing need to problematise and fill research gaps in existing literature thereby synthesising and expanding existing

knowledge [14]. One of the most common of these reviews, which also grounds a rigorous and authoritative delivery, is a systematic literature review (SLR) [15]. While there are quite a few approaches to conduct a SLR (i.e., SPAR-4-SLR, PSALSAR, etc [16], [17]), this paper followed the PRISMA Protocol for Systematic Literature Reviews. The following subsection will discuss the methods of this review.

2.1 Formulating the research question

To formulate the research question, the study employed the PICO mnemonic [18], [19], to illustrate its relevance in the field. The question was thus divided into the:

- i. **Population:** Research articles discussing the EHR phenomenon of interest
- ii. **Interest:** The phenomenon of interest EHR, and the concept of quality healthcare services delivery
- iii. **Context:** All concepts were reviewed in the context of quality healthcare services delivery
- iv. **Outcome:** The EHR benefits and constraints (influence) on quality healthcare services delivery.

2.2 Literature search strategy

The review followed the PRISMA protocol, which involves three main stages: literature identification, screening, and applying inclusion/exclusion criteria[20], [21]. Articles were sourced from top medical databases, CINAHL, PubMed, and Cochrane, to examine how EHR systems influence healthcare service quality. To incorporate interdisciplinary perspectives, relevant journals from the fields of Information Systems and Quality Management i.e., *Studies in Health Technology and Informatics* and *Journal of Nursing Management* were also included.

2.3 Screening, inclusion, and exclusion criteria

Although CINAHL and PubMed were sufficient for reviewing healthcare service quality, Cochrane was added due to its focus on systematic reviews. The initial search in Cochrane used the full review title to check for existing similar studies, yielding only 3 articles. A refined search using keywords “*Electronic Health Record systems*” AND “*quality [of] healthcare services delivery*” returned 14 articles, of which 8 were included in the review spanning 2014 and 2025. The same search strategy used in Cochrane was applied to CINAHL and PubMed, using the key terms “*Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems*” AND “*quality [of] healthcare services delivery*”, and limiting results to English, peer-reviewed articles published between 2014 and 2025.

Due to the large number of results, strict inclusion criteria were applied. Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of articles retrieved from the three databases Cochrane, CINAHL, and PubMed, selected for their relevance to nursing and healthcare research. The PRISMA chart outlines the systematic review process through identification, screening, and inclusion stages [22]. This review followed all six PRISMA stages, starting with framing the search string using MeSH terms in PubMed [23], to align with the research question. Stage 2 involved developing formal search strategies across

PubMed, CINAHL, and Cochrane. Cochrane was searched first to confirm the novelty of the review, revealing that while similar titles exist, none were conducted as systematic literature reviews (SLRs).

Fig 1. -PRISMA flow diagram 2020 (Adapted from Page et al., 2021).

2.4 Quality assessment data synthesis and analysis

In Stage 3 of the PRISMA protocol, refined search strategies were applied across PubMed, CINAHL, and Cochrane. While Cochrane yielded only 14 articles, PubMed

and CINAHL initially returned thousands. Using expanders and limiters via EBSCOhost, the results were narrowed to 149 empirical, English-language, peer-reviewed articles. After removing 31 duplicates and excluding 89 articles for reasons including lack of depth, relevance, or consistency, a final set of 29 articles was selected for review. In Stage 4, data extraction was guided by predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure relevance and quality. Stage 5 involved a rigorous quality assessment using CASP tools [24], resulting in the selection of 29 final articles (see Table 1). Stage 6 focused on synthesising the extracted data using meta-aggregation, identifying and summarising key findings into thematic insights [25]. While the literature search was rigorous, it was not exhaustive due to limitations such as time, access, and content overlap. To maintain quality, the review exercised discretion [26] in selecting the final 29 articles, focusing strictly on those explicitly linking EHR systems to healthcare service quality. Table 2 presents the thematic coding of these articles using the Gioia Methodology, which guided the development of analytical themes.

Author, Year	Method	Content relevance
(Al-Barnawi et al., 2019)	Case Study	EMR, Risk Management
(Al-Rawajfah & Tubaishat, 2019)	Survey	EHR, Health Informatics benefits for nursing
(Ammenwerth et al., 2021)	SLR	EHR, Patient-centred care
(Boyle et al., 2014)	SLR	EHR, smoking cessation, decision support system
(Byon et al., 2022)	Survey (CS)	EHR, Substance use tracking
(Do Carmo Alonso et al., 2020)	Design Scie.	EHR, Mental healthcare of youths
(Garcia et al., 2019)	Case Study	EHR, Opioid prescription tracking system
(Gonçalves-Bradley et al., 2020)	SLR	EHR, Telemedicine for communication facilitation
(Gordon et al., 2023)	SLR	EHR, Telehealth management for IBD
(Heisey-Grove et al., 2015)	Survey	EHR, Public health surveillance system
(Herrera et al., 2017)	SLR	EHR, Health policy and decision support systems
(Lekan et al., 2022)	SLR	EHR, Hospitalisation data management
(Lombardi et al., 2023)	Case Study	EHR, Social work systems integration
(Marca et al., 2014)	Survey	EHR, Health information management system
(McBride et al., 2018)	Case Study	EHR, Ethical issues with EHR use
(Monsen et al., 2014)	Case Study	EHR, Interoperability of EHR systems
(Odendaal et al., 2020)	SLR	mHealth, Primary healthcare giving services
(Palmer et al., 2020)	SLR	mHealth, Targeted comms for maternal health
(Palmer et al., 2021)	SLR	mHealth, Adherence to cardio medicine
(Pogorzelska-Maziarz et al., 2023)	Survey	EHR, Adoption by Home healthcare agencies
(Rezaeibagha et al., 2015)	SLR	EHR, Security and privacy, technical views
(Simons & Kohn, 2019)	Survey (CS)	EHR, Documentation of pregnancy intentions
(Straub et al., 2014)	Survey	EHR, Preconception Health Optimization
(Tubaishat, 2018)	Survey (CS)	EHR, Acceptance (TAM) of EHRs, PU & PEoU
(Tubaishat, 2019)	Not specific	EHR, Effects of EHRs on patient safety
(Vanek et al., 2016)	Survey	EHR, Nutrition documentation system
(Vasudevan et al., 2021)	SLR	mHealth, Birth and death notification
(Vreeman & Richoz, 2015)	Not specific	EHR, Vocabulary standardisation of EHRs.

Author, Year	Method	Content relevance
(Watters et al., 2016)	Not specific	EHR, impacts in enhancing cultural competence

Table 1. -Literature Review classification table

3 THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW CODING AND ANALYSIS

The Gioia Methodology (GM) is a methodology that advocates using systematically derived data that accounts for both *1st-order codes* [informant-based: in this case, faithfully coding verbatim from the articles] and *2nd-order themes* [researcher-based: using researcher discretion [26] and understandings [10]. Table 2. is a demonstration of the application of the GM to the 29 selected articles. The themes were qualitatively developed from the open coding of text in the 29 articles reviewed. First order codes were highlighted based on how they linked to the concepts of EHR and quality of healthcare services in the article's verbatim. From the initial codes some several second order themes were formulated [10]. Once those numerous first order codes and second order thematic areas were analysed for relationships, they were categorised according to similar inferences thereby formulating final major themes.

Source	First order code and second order themes (for benefits)	Theme
Rezaeibagha et al., 2015). Garcia et al., 2019). Do Carmo Alonso et al., 2020). Straub et al., 2014). Tubaishat, 2019). Simons & Kohn, 2019). Vreeman & Richoz, 2015).	Secure communication. Customised design. Improved patient safety through customised coordination. Data accessed via account log in. Medication errors are minimised. Helpful tool for planning and keeping accurate records. Because records are central, facility vocabulary becomes standardised, eliminating ambiguity. Tracking medical visits to avoid double booking and overdoses of medication administration.	Safety.
Do Carmo Alonso et al., 2020). Garcia et al., 2019) Vreeman & Richoz, 2015). Al-Rawajfah & Tubaishat, 2019). Byon et al., 2022). Simons & Kohn, 2019).	Improved patient safety through customised coordination. Supplements traditional surveillance. User specific design. Usability. Effective articulation. Access to concise information. Features that can improve care outcomes. Interoperability of the systems facilitate quick data sharing. Helpful tool for planning and keeping accurate records.	Effectiveness.
Vreeman & Richoz, 2015) Do Carmo Alonso et al., 2020). Garcia et al., 2019)	Features that can improve patient care outcomes. User specific design. Specific case information. Improved patient safety through customised coordination.	Patient-centredness.

	Because records are central , facility vocabulary becomes standardised, eliminating ambiguity .	
Do Carmo Alonso et al., 2020). Garcia et al., 2019). Tubaishat, 2018). Al-Rawajfah & Tubaishat, 2019). Byon et al., 2022).	Usability . Improved access . Specific case information. Information easily retrievable . Ease of use of the system. Interoperability of the systems facilitate quick data sharing.	Timeliness.
Do Carmo Alonso et al., 2020). Lombardi et al., 2023). Monsen et al., 2014). Tubaishat, 2019). Byon et al., 2022). Al-Rawajfah & Tubaishat, 2019). Vreeman & Richoz, 2015).	User specific design . Improved patient safety through customised coordination. Standardised sequential screening . Improved and standardised representation of information. The sustainability of data is improved . Interoperability of the systems facilitate quick data sharing . Because records are central , facility vocabulary becomes standardised, eliminating ambiguity . Data cleaning, importing, merging, and analysis features bring great advantage.	Equitability.
Garcia et al., 2019) Do Carmo Alonso et al., 2020). Lombardi et al., 2023) Monsen et al., 2014). Al-Rawajfah & Tubaishat, 2019). Simons & Kohn, 2019).	Improved patient safety through customised coordination . User specific design . Usability . Access to concise information. Specific case information . Helpful documentation . Improved and standardised representation of information . Interoperability of the systems facilitate quick data sharing. Helpful tool for planning and keeping accurate records.	Efficiency.

Table 2. -Thematic Analysis table generated from the reviewed articles

4 DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents the benefits of EHR system adoption, implementation, and use, highlighting their positive effects on healthcare quality. Thematic analysis of 29 articles using the Gioia Methodology revealed six interconnected themes namely: *safety*, *effectiveness*, *patient-centredness*, *timeliness*, *equitability*, and *efficiency*. These themes often overlapped or complemented each other, for example, effectiveness was closely tied to efficiency, and system security influenced both safety and information accessibility. Overall, the themes collectively demonstrate how EHR systems enhance healthcare service quality.

4.1 Safety

EHR use supports patient safety by having features that reduce the possibility of errors in medical care. Common patient safety functions in EHRs can support medical care through provision of accurate information to medicines that have been administered and those that remain without nursing staff having to rely on their minds and manual decentralised systems [27]. Because of customisation features, safety in healthcare can also be increased by informing the clinician of high-risk medications that are not appropriate for a particular patient because of allergies or other health conditions. Some of the high-leverage patient safety functions alert when ages or lab results indicate incorrect dosages, conflicting drug to drug interactions, custom alerts the pharmacists use, and listing a patient's medications. In that way, there is reduced duplication of tests and medication, reduced hospital admissions and hospital emergency department visits, thereby improving adherence to established care guidelines.

4.2 Effectiveness

The safety discussion has a direct link to the effectiveness of services as well. Adherence to established care guidelines help enhance effectiveness of facility functions. EHRs in healthcare greatly improve workflow and support more accurate and timely interventions in the health setting because they capture, and display data obtained at the point of initial care. Nursing staff have access to guidelines and best practices provided through Clinical Decision Support Systems, which can help them make more effective care decisions supported by evidence. Such information can make EHRs "smarter" and can show physicians the best care options for a person according to that person's customised health status [28]. With their ability to integrate evidence-based guidelines into EHR systems, physicians can have their computers remind them to do what is required for the given patient at the appropriate time.

4.3 Patient-centredness

Patient-centred care emphasises active patient involvement in healthcare decision-making [29], supported by transparent and accessible health information. EHR systems enhance this by enabling secure e-consultations, improving coordination among providers, and empowering patients. However, shared EHRs must balance accessibility with privacy and data security [27]. Patients should have control over who accesses their information, ensuring confidentiality and trust. When properly managed, these features of EHRs contribute to better patient outcomes and satisfaction [30].

4.4 Timeliness

Timeliness, or reducing patient waiting time for receiving care, demonstrates enhanced access to care [28]. EHRs integrate clinical information to be utilised whenever care is delivered, making the patient's most relevant records instantly available, and they reduce the need to reschedule and wait for another office visit unless there is need. A busy specialist can adjust his or her intake schedule due to a patient's status, realise they

need assistance, and admit them or refer them to an emergency department. Healthcare quality also should enable full access to comprehensive and coordinated care across different settings, in which all patients are able to access services regardless of health or background. Availability of diagnostic history, surgical and other procedures (and results), medications, allergies, and disease history, contact numbers, insurance information, and advance directives concurrently across different system platforms can all be provided automatically to expedite timely access to the care needed.

4.5 Equitability

EHRs can help facilitate the secure, comprehensive, and systematic storage of health information, while also enabling complete and continuous documentation for the caregivers, allowing a more collaborative approach to provide care for the patient. This standardisation but personified experience improves the equitability of the system especially considering the different needs of individual patients [31]. However, unique patient identifiers and accurate patient matching are required to correctly link and manage patient data across different EHR systems to carry out a multi-discipline treatment plan. The ability to share such complete and continuous patient data can give physicians the clinical context to better understand and interpret individual patient needs. Gaps in information may also be identified, where patients on new treatments, for example, show adverse drug reactions after changes occur.

4.6 Efficiency

EHRs also analyse data, which can be used to assess overall healthcare costs and outcomes, and to identify trends and treatments that make a difference. This is critical for more informed clinical decision-making and to be more efficient by identifying the best treatment in relation to cost. It is also helpful tool for planning and keeping accurate records [32]. Meanwhile, an increasing number of studies have shown that EHR adoption is associated with improved adherence to disease management guidelines and performance on a number of quality metrics, innovation, reduced hospital readmissions, reduced financial costs, and better management of chronic diseases [33], [34], [35], [36]. While other studies have argued these findings in contrast, most suggest that benefits in the quality of care can be achieved through effective use of EHR systems.

There were several studies that reported on the challenges of the systems. For instance, the issue of ethical challenges surrounding patient information was one of the problems discussed [37]. Byon and others also raised that if data is entered incorrectly, this could result in detrimental consequences [38]. Likewise, since the systems are more likely to be hosted on the cloud, or accessed via the internet, it was reported that healthcare facilities could face challenges like denial of service when systems are down, or attacks from outside hackers [39]. Similarly, technical and infrastructural issues were reported to be some of the challenges associated with the EHRM systems [40].

5 CONCLUSION

This study examined the potential in the adoption, implementation, and use of Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems to improve healthcare quality while acknowledging associated challenges. Evidence from research between 2014 and 2025 highlights benefits such as enhanced [information] *safety*, *effective* and *efficient* [processes], *patient-centredness* [for easy access to data and customisation], *timely* and *equitable* services delivery [mitigating processes disharmony]. Although EHR systems are not universally applicable due to contextual variability across institutions and systems, the facilities already using them shared these common thematic areas. Similarly, extant literature revealed the same results, as most studies agreed to all or at the least four of the six themes on how employment of EHR systems enhance healthcare services delivery. The review calls for further investigation using large-scale quantitative or mixed-method approaches, as the current study relied solely on qualitative methods. Comprehensive evaluation remains essential for informed decision-making and maximising EHR systems' impact in healthcare services delivery.

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